

CHARACTERISATION OF VISCOELASTIC MATERIAL PROPERTIES DURING CURING PROCESSES

Sibin Saseendran^{1,2}, Maciej Wysocki^{1,3} and Janis Varna²

¹ Swerea SICOMP, Box 271, 941 26 Piteå, Sweden

Email: sibin.saseendran@swerea.se, web page: <http://www.swerea.se/sicomp/>

² Department of Engineering Sciences and Mathematics, Luleå University of Technology
971 87 Luleå, Sweden

Email: janis.varna@ltu.se, web page: <http://www.ltu.se>

³ Department of Applied Mechanics, Chalmers University of Technology
Hörsalsvägen 7a, SE-412 96 Göteborg, Sweden

Email: maciej.wysocki@swerea.se / wysocki@chalmers.se, web page: <http://www.chalmers.se>

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ABSTRACT

The present contribution is toward systematic characterisation of the thermo-viscoelastic properties of a curing epoxy resin system, here we use Huntsman LY5052/HY5052 as model material. The main focus is to verify the existence of equivalence relation (linearity) between time, temperature and degree (time) of cure. As a starting point, the cure kinetics behaviour of the model material has been characterised using DSC equipment and the results have been used to identify parameters in a generic Kamal cure kinetics model. In the subsequent work the DSC data and Kamal model was used to carefully monitor the degree of cure in the resin in all the subsequent experiments. The thermo-viscoelastic response of the curing epoxy was characterised using a dynamic mechanical thermal analyser (DMTA). All the DMTA experiments were focused on rubbery and glassy states only, were the material was subject to tests at various isothermal and non-isothermal loading conditions. The results were used to investigate the linearity between the three factors above (time, temperature and curing time). To summarize, the results indicate that these three parameters indeed obey a linear relationship in the linear viscoelastic regime.

1 INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, composites have been developed using trial and error methods resulting in an expensive development process. This is in particular true for the development of manufacturing processes, where many experimental loops are necessary before an efficient manufacturing process is established [1-2]. Therefore, the present trend in composites design is toward virtual methods, in particular within the aerospace and transportation industry, which pushes the boundaries of virtual CAE towards new modelling areas. However to enable the aforementioned trend it is necessary to increase understanding of the physics of phenomena. New modelling methodologies and tools are necessary to reduce developmental costs incurred by developing new components. One such area considered here is the prediction of manufacturing induced residual stresses and their evolution with time.

Experimental studies have been performed in order to characterise the development of viscoelastic properties during cure. Eom et al. [3], have characterised in a rheometer, the viscoelasticity development during curing process with various curing temperatures. The obtained values relate to the shear storage modulus development over the curing process. Eom et al. have been able to determine that the shift factors have a linear relationship with cure temperatures using time-temperature superposition. In spite of being fairly complete the work by Eom et al. does not consider a few fundamental aspects, such as they don't justify the VE assumption of the work, beside only

considering shear storage modulus. Further, they were unable to prove that the material is independent of its curing history.

O'Brien et al. [4] have performed experiments with neat epoxy resins with a single cure temperature and have found that the cure state has no effect on the elastic response of the material. Moreover O'Brien et al. has only focussed on one cure temperature to assess the viscoelastic response of the epoxy system which is quite insufficient while determining the role of cure temperature in viscoelastic response development. O'Brien et al. have also noted that the peak equilibrium relaxation modulus varies significantly between the fully cured and uncured states and hence hinting at a possible interdependence of the equilibrium modulus and degree of cure.

Further, in the work by Thorpe and Pousartip [5], an attempt to develop a model based on a carbon fibre backed epoxy system was performed. Characterisation was performed in the solid state in a DMA and in the liquid state for a neat resin in a rheometer. The findings have concluded that a thermo-rheologically simple time-temperature superposition is insufficient to characterise viscoelastic behaviour. The study has also concluded that the glassy state modulus is independent of the degree of cure, a behaviour which is also confirmed by Sadeghinia et al. [6] alternatively in the shear modulus domain. Furthermore it is thought that using a carbon fibre backed resin system as opposed to a neat resin sample may compromise results corresponding to the storage modulus when tests have been performed in the solid state. To isolate the storage modulus of the resin from the storage modulus of the composite, this work has used a general rule of mixtures where the transverse modulus and fibre volume fractions have been used based on assumptions without experimental confirmation.

Suzuki et al. [7] have reported that the form of a master curve generated through time-temperature superposition principles is dependent on the cure temperature and time and both factors are to be considered separately. However in their work, Suzuki et al. have not made an attempt to study cure kinetics and subsequent comparisons with the cure state of the resin. Experiments have been performed in the report based on temperature and time explicitly.

In the work by Simon et al. [8], a model for the calculation of the evolution of shear storage modulus that takes inputs of cure kinetics from a conventional model has been formulated. This model incorporates time-temperature superposition and time-cure state superposition in thermosets. However the model has been only tested at a single frequency of 1Hz in a rheometer, to which the model agreed well with experimental data and it is unclear if the same is applicable to higher or lower frequencies. An attempt to model a cure dependent evolution of the storage modulus in a high temperature epoxy system based on a modified form of the Kohlrausch-Williams-Watts (KWW) equations has been performed in the work by Zarrelli et al. [9].

Yeong et al. [10] have ascertained that since most of the residual stresses develop at post-gelation it is ideal to look for ways to model stress relaxation at such post-gelation conditions. Their effort focussed primarily on the stress relaxation behaviour of epoxy resin samples that have been cured to a particular degree of cure using several different temperatures to cure. The fundamental assumption in this paper is that the relaxation modulus depends on the cure state on an a priori basis, which could be problematic since a real time assessment on the cure state is necessary for viscoelastic update of the modulus.

Adolf and Martin [11] have done preliminary assessment of the influence of cure on viscoelastic properties by developing a time-cure superposition method. This method uses horizontal and vertical shifting of DMA data to arrive at master curves and the approximation uses power law fitting rather than conventional Prony series fitting. The vertical shift accounts for the change in the equilibrium modulus with changing degree of cure which has never been accounted for in some other similar works. They have worked on the shear modulus domain and have not conducted an in-depth analysis of the cure profile of the material under test. They have ascertained that viscoelastic functions at differing extents of reaction should superpose if the appropriate vertical and horizontal shifts are applied to the DMA data.

The present contribution is toward systematic characterisation of the thermo-viscoelastic properties of a curing epoxy resin system. Characterising the thermo-viscoelastic solid behaviour is performed using a dynamic mechanical analyser. The aim of this work is to investigate the dependence of the viscoelastic response on time, temperature and degree (time) of cure. In particular, the aim is to investigate the linearity between these three parameters. The approach adapted in this study is

construct and compare "super master curves" using two different sets of experimental result obtained using various isothermal and non-isothermal loading conditions. In the first case, a master curve for a given cure and test temperature is obtained by shifting the curves corresponding to different cure times. Then the master curves for different temperatures are reduced to a "super-master curve 1" for a certain reference temperature. In the second case, a master curve for certain curing condition is constructed and then a "super-master curve 2" for a certain reference curing time and temperature. Ideally for linearly thermo-viscoelastic material, both experimental sets should lead to the same result - coinciding "super-master" curves 1 and 2.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material

The resin system used for the characterisation of the thermo-viscoelasticity of a curing epoxy system consisted of LY5052 epoxy with HY5052 hardener from Huntsman. Prior any experimental procedure, the resin was mixed in the ratio 100:38 by weight and stirred thoroughly, taking care not to include air bubbles. In total 18 samples was mixed and prepared for the DSC and 59 for the DMTA experiments.

2.2 DSC

The cure kinetics profiling was performed using a Diamond series DSC instrument from Perkin-Elmer. The samples for the DSC instrument were placed on a steel sample pans and weighed on a Mettler-Toledo AE240 digital scale. The cure kinetics profiling was performed for four different temperatures, 23°C, 40°C, 60°C and 80°C in two stages. The method adopted for 23°C case was the following: three samples were firstly cured within the DSC for a predetermined time to obtain the residual heat of reaction and obtain a certain degree of cure. The predetermined times have been chosen as 2, 4, 6, 12 and 24 hours. After each pre-curing stage a dynamic temperature scan from 0°C to 200°C, at the rate of 10°C/min, was performed to obtain the residual heat of reaction. Another set of three samples containing uncured resins were put through the same dynamic temperature scan parameters as the case for 23°C to obtain the average total heat of reaction for the system.

The second stage of DSC scanning was performed to obtain the heat of reaction for the rest of the temperatures, viz. 40°C, 60°C and 80°C. For this, isothermal scans were performed at the corresponding temperatures until equilibrium was attained. The sample was heated as quickly as possible to the corresponding temperatures so that no heat of reaction was lost during the heating up phase of the scan. The time required to attain equilibrium varies with temperature, with higher temperatures taking shorter times to attain equilibrium due to increased rate of crosslinking reactions and vice-versa.

Epoxy resin curing is an exothermic reaction and thermosetting. Thermoset cure kinetics is typically modelled using nth-order or autocatalytic kinetic schemes in isothermal analysis [12-13]. Resins obeying nth-order kinetics show a maximum reaction rate at $t=0$. In this work we have chosen to use a well established cure kinetic model by Kamal which describes the reaction rate as an analytical function of temperature and degree of cure as detailed in equation (1)[12],

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt}(T, \alpha) = Ae^{-\frac{B}{RT}}(\alpha^m)(\alpha_{T_g} - \alpha)^n \quad (1)$$

where α is the degree of cure, A is the pre-exponential rate constant (also called the collision frequency factor [14]), T is the temperature in Kelvins, B is the reaction energy, R is the ideal gas constant, m and n are constants independent of cure temperature that are obtained from fitting experimental data from the DSC using standard least-squares fit. Moreover, the α is defined as

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{H}{H_{tot}} \quad (2)$$

where H is the residual heat of reaction and H_{tot} is the total heat of reaction. $\alpha_{(T_g)}$ is defined as the degree of cure attained for curing at various temperatures such that the material is in glassy state at the end of the curing cycle, i.e. $T_{cure} \leq T_g$. In principle, $\alpha_{(T_g)}$ is the degree of cure at which the material becomes glassy for a certain curing temperature. The values for $\alpha_{(T_g)}$ are obtained for each cure temperature T_{cure} from the isothermal DSC experiments performed and fitted linearly.

2.3 DMTA

The thermo-viscoelastic characterisation of the resin system was performed using a TA Instruments Q800 DMA instrument. The choice of clamp for measurement was limited to a 3-point bending mode and single cantilever mode. Prior to the actual material characterisation, two different clamp geometries were evaluated for their characteristics. The procedure consisted of a frequency scan at various temperatures to obtain a master curve using fully cured neat resin samples of LY5052/HY5052. The scan was performed at a frequency range of 200Hz, 100Hz, 10Hz, 1Hz, 0.1Hz and 0.01Hz and a temperature range of 23°C to 200°C in 10°C increments. The test conditions were identical for both 3-point bending mode and single cantilever mode. We have observed that the 3-point bend mode induces scatter in the results at higher temperatures. Therefore, the subsequent experiments were performed using single cantilever mode.

The experiments performed using the single cantilever mode required the use of uncured resin samples, consequently a method of manufacturing samples was devised such that the samples could be manufactured quickly and easily without an intermediate stage of making plates and cutting them down to size, which would be difficult considering that the samples are not fully cured. In order to efficiently prepare cantilever samples of uncured resin, moulds were made from a silicone rubber. The dimensions of the tool were designed so that the samples have dimensions of 17.5mm x 12.8mm x 3mm. These dimensions were similar to the sample dimensions as specified by TA Instruments for single cantilever mode sample 17.5mm x 12.76mm x 3.19mm. The mould was then sandwiched between two plates of Teflon coated steel. The assembly was then clamped securely to prevent leakage once the mixed resin is poured into the mould. The mould assembly was then preheated to the required temperature in a convection oven before the resin is poured into it. Once the resin was poured into the mould, it was left to cure for various predetermined times and temperatures to attain a certain degree of cure. When the predetermined curing time has been reached, the mould was removed from the oven and the samples were cooled instantly using a coolant spray to prevent additional curing and ‘peeled’ out from the mould. Three samples were produced at a time with identical degrees of cure with this method, although more could be made. The samples were then polished at the sides using a Struers Rotapol-1 polishing machine following which they are ready for DMTA testing. The samples were assessed visually to determine if they deformed or were damaged while being mounted on to the DMTA especially for samples that had low degrees of cure since they were most often in the transition or rubbery zones.

Table 1: Curing temperature and time.

Temperatures	Curing times (hours)	Total number of samples
23°C	14.75; 17; 18; 19; 21; 24	6
40°C	3.5; 4; 4.5; 5; 5.5; 6; 6.5; 7; 7.5	9
60°C	1.25; 1.5; 1.75; 2; 2.25; 2.5; 3	28
80°C	0.5; 0.75; 1; 1.25	16

Similarly to the DSC experiments, the DMTA experiments have been split into two different approaches. In the first set, the samples were evaluated at a constant temperature, viz. 23°C, 40°C, 60°C and 80°C in order to induce a predetermined degree of cure and observe how the modulus evolves with cure. Table 1 shows the curing times at each of the four temperatures before testing. In the second set the samples were evaluated for the effect of varying temperatures. In the first set, the samples that were cured at a particular temperature were also tested at the same temperature. The frequency scan range for all the experiments are; 200Hz, 100Hz, 10Hz, 1Hz, 0.1Hz and 0.05Hz, performed in a descending order. The second set of experiments was performed for 60°C and 80°C

cure temperatures only. The curing times are identical to the previous experiments; however, they were evaluated at different temperatures, viz. 23°C, 40°C, 60°C and 80°C. To be more precise, samples cured at 60°C for 1.5 hours were tested at 23°C, 40°C, 60°C and 80°C for instance. Care was taken to ensure constant degree of cure during the experiments. This was achieved by using one sample for each temperature. Since each of the DMA tests last approximately 10 minutes, the difference in degrees of cure from start to finish is negligible as confirmed by the DSC characterisation. The applied deflection on the sample was in the order of 0.01% in all DMA tests.

Figure 1: Schematic of the experimental method and shifting procedures applied.

In the first approach, we intend to assess the cure time (and hence consequently, degree of cure)/frequency for a given temperature while in the second experiment we assess and characterise the temperature/frequency at a given time and temperature. This work is in particular intended to characterise the linearity of viscoelastic material properties of the resin system in consideration. Usually we talk about time-temperature superposition for response characterisation, in the present contribution however we examine the time-temperature-DoC (Degree of Cure) superposition. However, as will be described later in the paper, it seems that using cure time instead of DoC results in linear shift functions between time, temperature and cure time. Since DoC is a direct function of the cure time, we modify the present work by speaking in terms of time/temperature/cure time. Thus, in the present paper we assume that only the reduced time depends on the curing parameters. Master curves can be obtained by shifting the curves in the frequency domain twice in the horizontal direction, the first being for testing at different test temperatures and the second for different curing states. A schematic of the two-pronged approach procedure is depicted in Fig. 1.

3 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 DSC

The total heat of reaction, H_{tot} (cf. equation 2), for the presently considered resin system has been determined to be 482 J/g. The experimental data from the DSC experiment are presented in Fig. 2 together with the fitted Kamal model. The fitting was performed against the data from the experiments performed at 40, 60 and 80°C. The fitted parameters for the generic Kamal (Eq. 1) are shown in Table 2. Moreover, in Fig. 2 the Kamal model is assessed against the data from the 23°C experiment. The model shows good agreement with the corresponding experimental data. The maximum degree of cure at equilibrium has been plotted as a function of the curing temperature in Fig. 3. This is to predict the maximum degree of cure, α_{max} for a particular temperature.

Figure 2: DSC data and corresponding Kamal model.

Table 2: Parameters for the generic Kamal model.

Parameter	Value
$A[1/s]$	274906.7
$B[J/mol]$	54888.35
m	0.25
n	1.01

Figure 3: Maximum degree of cure vs. cure temperature based on DSC data.

3.2 DMTA - approach 1

The first set of experiments described in the previous section has been performed to determine the effects of the curing time on the viscoelastic behaviour at the curing temperature. In consequence, the raw data from each temperature has been used to construct master curves by shifting the data in the curing time domain. The reference curve that has been chosen for each of the temperatures was chosen in such a way that the degree of cure is approximately 80-85% as determined by the cure kinetic model. In Fig. 4, each master curve is accompanied by cure time shift factors necessary to achieve the shift. The shifting procedure was performed manually and the curves are generated based on how well they fit with respect to one another. The shift factors for each case have also been constructed to visualize the general behaviour of the shift with respect to the curing time. This could be easily correlated to the degree of cure as it could be determined from the cure kinetics model. The shift factors for the first set of experiments are also shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Master curves obtained by shifting the curing time for a) 25°C, b) 40°C, c) 60°C and d) 80°C. The shift factors used for the superposition are also shown (arrows indicate corresponding axes).

To determine how the master curves look like in each case when an identical state of cure is selected, a reference cure state was chosen at 80%. The results have been depicted in Fig. 5 while the time of cure corresponding to 80% for each temperature is detailed in Table 3.

Figure 5: Master curves for each temperatures using 80% cure as reference.

Table 3: Time required to attain 80% degree of cure for each temperature.

Temperature	Time to attain 80% α (in minutes)
23°C	1221
40°C	288
60°C	68
80°C	19.5

Following the shifting of the master curves into a position which represents 80% state of cure, the individual master curves are shifted again horizontally, using 23°C (room temperature) as a reference state. This shifting result of data for different temperature is shown in Fig. 6a. The comparison of the shift factors used for the second shift has been shown in Fig. 6b.

Figure 6: Super-master curve at 23°C (room temperature) and second shift factors.

3.2 DMTA - approach 2

The second approach is to develop and generate master curves for samples that have been cured to a certain degree of cure at a particular temperature and tested at various temperatures. The cure temperatures were 60°C and 80°C. For each degree of cure (T_c and t_c) the generated curves for different test temperatures T were shifted in the frequency domain to construct the individual master curves. It was done for both 60°C and 80°C cases and for different curing times as shown in Fig. 7. For all cases the curve representing 23°C testing temperature was chosen as the reference curve for the construction of master curves.

Figure 7: Master curves for a) 60°C and b) 80°C relating to various degrees of cure.

The shift factors for each of the cases relating to both 60°C and 80°C experiments are obtained based on the test temperatures at which the experiments were performed. The temperature shift factors for the master curves put together are shown in Fig. 8. The shift factors show the shift in temperature for each of the individual master curve represented in Fig. 7. It is observed that the shift factors do not change significantly for each curing time for both cases and the general behaviour to be linear across various temperatures. Hence irrespective of cure temperature (T_c), the shift factors can be assumed constant for a given T .

Figure 8: Shift factors for (a) 60°C and (b) 80°.

Figure 9: Super-master curves for (a) 60°C and (b) 80°C referenced at 80% degree of cure together with the relative shift factors (arrows indicates the axes).

Finally, as a last step the master curves obtained from the preceding operations for 60°C and 80°C were shifted once again in curing time. This second shifting was performed to obtain a single super-master curve. The reference for this operation was chosen to be the time of cure corresponding to 80% degree of cure. The final shifted compound curves for each temperature are represented in Fig. 9, along with the corresponding compound shift factors for each cure time.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Figure 10. Super-master curves constructed from dataset 1 and 2.

The present work supports the assumption that the LY5052 epoxy resin system shows linear elastic behaviour in the glass region and that the time to cure is independent of the cure history. Moreover, we also see evidence that the studied material is rheologically simple and that there indeed is a linear relationship between strain rate (time), temperature and degree of cure (via time of cure). The super-master curves obtained after shifting to 80% degree of cure for both datasets are shown in Fig. 10. The super master curves are virtually identical at the chosen state of cure of 80% irrespective of the experimental approach, c.f. the flow diagram in Fig. 1. The fact that the compound shift factors shown in Figs. 6 and 8 are equal, also supports the assumption of rheologically simple resin system.

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